

Software at NASA: Lightning Breakout 2A

Mission-related software: Part 2

CUBES

echusOverlook (eO): Open-Source Knowledge-Base For Techno-Economic Analysis and Simulation of Human Exploration Operations

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Electronic Data Sheets for Interoperable Instrument Flight Software


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<ContainerDataType baseType="JENA/PACKET UTILISATION/HDR_TC_PKT"
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  <Entry byteCount"/>
  <Entry guideStarIndex">
</EntryList>
</ContainerDataType>
```

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The Problem

1. Create a new instrument

2. Describe the instrument using documents

3. Interpret the docs to write software

A Better Solution

Facilitates virtual integration

Ensures compatibility

Promotes reusability

Simplifies data sharing

Reduces dev time

Enables easier maintenance

The Best Solution

What we need

Authoring tool to create new Data Sheets

Dictionary of Terms for a formalized vocabulary

Offers an expressive syntax based on semantic web.

Capture complex domain concepts, relationships, and constraints.

Generate stakeholder views and flight code.

Supports semantic reasoning and inference over a Data Sheet for verification and validation.

Perform analysis on the interoperability of the design.

Evolution of NASA's core Flight System (cFS) for the Mission of Tomorrow

Goddard Space Flight Center
Flight Software Systems Branch
Code 582

Full Presentation:

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core Flight System (cFS): Embedded software framework for spacecraft, instruments, and systems.

cFS named by the International Software System Interoperability Standards (ISwSIS) as the standard framework for Flight Software and is likely the most used Flight Software system in the world. NASA 2020 Software of the Year Award winner!

cFS is evolving to meet the needs of tomorrow's science mission, with capability including:

Support for next-gen hardware such as NASA's High Performance Spaceflight Computing (HPSC) platform:

- Heavily parallelized onboard operations
- AI / ML enabled by hardware vector acceleration
- Split architectures such as real-time spacecraft control and science processing on a single chip
- Hardware fault tolerance, cryptography, etc.
- Enable onboard AI, edge computing, and more!

Standardized onboard scripting for nominal mission control without reliance on ground contacts

- Scripts written in Lua, with other languages as potential future expansions
- Standardized capability that can interface with core apps and mission apps with EDS databases
- Scripts are updateable by engineers or flight ops

Multi-purpose Machine Learning inference engine

- Load domain-specific or reusable ground-trained model
- Run on advanced multi-core CPU or offload to GPU / FPGA
- Utilize Tensorflow Lite / OpenXLA under the hood
- Do the science processing onboard!

Flight System Hardening

- Protect our missions from threats so they can continue doing science for years to come
- Improve authentication, encryption, and communication onboard following the principle of least privilege
- Upgrades can also sandbox onboard ML to safely raise TRL level

App Store

- Centralize Flight Software capability developed across NASA to better share between projects and reduce duplication

The cFS team is looking for partners to help us drive technology forward to support the science missions to come

autoNGC: Autonomous Navigation, Guidance, and Control Software in a Low SWaP Box

Link to [2024 Flight Software Workshop Presentation](#)

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NASA/GSFC

Software for the NASA SMD Workshop
May 7-9, 2024

What is autoNGC?

An **onboard** software application suite built on the core Flight System (cFS) and flight hardware solution that performs real-time **autonomous** spacecraft navigation, guidance, and control (NGC)

Why autoNGC?

- Reduce reliance on over-subscribed ground assets and ground operators
- Enable new mission capabilities
 - Low latency mission operations
 - Complex missions at far distances, e.g., Touch-and-Go (TAG) Guidance
 - In-situ planning and execution, important for crewed missions
 - Distributed Systems Missions (DSMs)
 - ~~Dynamic replanning and reallocation of orbital assets~~

Key autoNGC Flight Software Libraries

- Goddard Enhanced Onboard Navigation System (GEONS) – extended Kalman filter
 - Nominal and weak signal GNSS
 - Terrain Relative Navigation
 - Limb/centroiding optical navigation
 - 1-way forward and 2-way ground & relay
 - Celestial object bearing
 - Accelerometer
 - LiDAR
- cFS Goddard Image Analysis and Navigation Tool (cGIANT) – advanced image processing

autoNGC Attributes:

- Resilient across multiple orbit regimes
- Heritage Design
- Plug-n-play customizable architecture
- Fault Tolerant Autonomy
- Low SWaP-C Hardware Implementation

Lunar Browser trajectory tool

A NASA Ames Flight Dynamics team tool

Anthony Genova
Dylan Morrison-Fogel
Paul Levinson-Muth
Andres Dono Perez
Regina Blue

For more detailed information on the Lunar Browser tool, see this AIAA SciTech paper:

[Transfers from TLI to Lunar Frozen Orbits with Applications to NASA's CLPS & ARTEMIS Programs \(aiaa.org\)](#)

To learn more about the NASA Ames Flight Dynamics Team:

[Ames Flight Dynamics \(FD\) - NASA](#)

Genova, A. L., Morrison-Fogel, D., & Levinson-Muth, P., "Transfers from TLI to Lunar Frozen Orbits with Applications to NASA's CLPS & Artemis Programs," AAS/AIAA Space Flight Mech. Mtg., Orlando, FL, Jan. 8-12, 2024

Earth-to-Moon transfer trajectory visualizations & animations

Direct output

Applicable studies

Lunar Browser

Populates Global Solution Space of Earth-Moon transfer trajectories & communication windows over multi-year period to evaluate complex and diverse CLPS requirements, proposals, and missions

>100,000 trajectories generated to date

Applicable studies

Relative Motion collision assessment & prevention

Lunar Landing Windows

Extended solutions with high-fidelity phasing lunar orbits preceding lighting-constrained landings

Lunar Terrain Analysis

Highest resolution data available used with lighting, timing, & other constraints

Database of Earth-Moon Trajectories

Lunar Browser can be operated via GUI with filters & logic control

Interface

Software for CubeSat Operations for Earth and (Other) Planetary Science

The Distributed Spacecraft Autonomy (DSA)

Caleb Adams, Project Manager | Jeremy Frank, Deputy Project Manager

Distributed Spacecraft Autonomy

NASA's Distributed Spacecraft Autonomy (DSA) Project developed and demonstrated software to enhance multi-spacecraft mission adaptability, efficiently allocate tasks between spacecraft using ad-hoc networking, and enable human-swarm commanding of Distributed Space Missions.

DSA-Starling is a software payload on the Starling space mission, consisting of 4 spacecraft in Low Earth Orbit. DSA-Starling uses the GPS receivers as a science instrument; DSA allocates GPS satellites to spacecraft in a fully distributed and autonomous manner, at a cadence of 1 Hz.

DSA-LPNT is a processor-in-the-loop scalability study building on the same DSA-Starling software suite. DSA-LPNT demonstrates fully distributed, multi-spacecraft localization using space-to-space radio communications as inputs to state-estimation. DSA-LPNT increases the size and scale of the mission (20-100 spacecraft), and increases complexity (reorienting communication antennas instead of monitoring GPSIDs).

DSA software is implemented as Core Flight Software (cFS) applications, and uses open-source automated reasoning and communications software.

Enabling Software Capabilities for Artemis Science Teams

Intelligent Long Endurance Observing System (ILEOS)

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Intelligent Systems Division
NASA Ames Research Center

IMPACT: (1) Reduced cost for Earth observations, (2) continuous observations, and (3) improved science outcomes

Software for SMD Workshop | May 8, 2024

ILEOS Pipeline

ILEOS will provide a science activity planning system to enable NOS by fusing coarse-grained data

Playbook

a planning, scheduling and execution tool
for flagship missions and small projects alike

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NASA Ames Research Center

Science Mission Directorate Workshop 2024

Playbook

COCPIT: Playbook for Mars2020

Payload 4

Dra Pre-Flight

12:00 to 13:00 (01:00:00)

Info

Name: Dra Pre-Flight

Id: 793eb4e9-ec4c-4fc6-a793-bfc7d935cd6f

PlanUnitType: Activity

Color: [Blue]

Schedule

Start: 2022-10-02 12:00

End: 2022-10-02 13:00

Duration: 01:00

Notes

Notes

Parameters

Task List:

Distance:

Time Critical:

Mandatory:

Payload: DraGMet

Chat with text, audio, photos, attachments and communication delay

Chat with text, audio, photos, attachments and communication delay

Documents/procedures repository and management, links from activities

Procedure	Activities Linked	Last Updated
13-0000 Daily Summary Mission Data	1	2024-04-29 12:08
1.101 NEEMO Mission Rules	0	2024-04-29 12:08
1.102 Mission Procedures	0	2024-04-29 12:08
2.101 Playback Queue Reference Cue Card	2	2024-04-29 12:08
2.104 Control Queue	0	2024-04-29 12:08
3.101 Playback Autonomy Plan Procedures	1	2024-04-29 12:08
3.108 Playback Autonomy Functional Status	0	2024-04-29 12:08
3.109 Video VideoReference Installation	3	2024-04-29 12:08
4.101 NEEMO Strategy System Linkages	9	2024-04-29 12:08
4.101 CREW CAMERA PROCEDURE	17	2024-04-29 12:08
4.104 Camera SACS Link A Manual	0	2024-04-29 12:08
4.104 Gopher SACS A Slave Link A Manual	2	2024-04-29 12:08
4.105 Gopher SACS A Slave Queue Start Guide	0	2024-04-29 12:08
4.105 Gopher SACS A Slave Queue Start Guide	0	2024-04-29 12:08
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4.105 NEEMO EVA CueCards MGR	16	2024-04-29 12:08
4.105 EVA Playbook	10	2024-04-29 12:08
4.201 IX Reclamation	11	2024-04-29 12:08
4.202 Orion MCT	11	2024-04-29 12:08
4.301 IX Autost System Cue Card	0	2024-04-29 12:08
4.401 NEEMO EVA ESA LESA Cue Card	0	2024-04-29 12:08
4.404 NEEMO EVA ESA Strategy System Cue Card	0	2024-04-29 12:08

Documents/procedures repository and management, links from activities

SMD: Mars2020, CLPS, BASALT
Analog: HERA, CHAPEA, NEEMO

Name	Start	Const...	De...	Da...
Entry/Descent	2022-10-01 07:00		01:30	
Landing	2022-10-01 08:30		01:00	
Beep	2022-10-01 09:30		00:30	
ENG Keepout	2022-10-01 10:00		00:30	
Thermal Mgr	2022-10-01 10:30	1	02:30	
DraMS Power Up	2022-10-01 11:30	1	00:15	
DraCO Power Up	2022-10-01 11:45	1	00:15	
D Initialization	2022-10-01 11:45	2	01:00	
DraMS Power Up	2022-10-01 12:00	1	00:15	
D Initialization	2022-10-01 12:00	2	01:00	
DraMet Power Up	2022-10-01 12:15	1	00:15	
Dra Initialization	2022-10-01 12:15	2	01:00	
DragonCam Power Up	2022-10-01 12:30	1	00:15	
DraD Initialization	2022-10-01 12:30	2	01:00	
DraG Initialization	2022-10-01 12:45	2	01:00	
D Checkout	2022-10-01 12:45	4	05:00	
D Checkout	2022-10-01 13:00	4	05:00	

Timeline: Collaborative plan editing, constraint checking and violation visualization, customizable parameters, tracking of activity status, timeline notes, modeling of numeric resources (e.g., power, data), role-based permissions, human-centered design and more!

SMD: Mars2020, CLPS, BASALT
Analog: HERA, CHAPEA, NEEMO

Open Source Multi-Mission Software: the MMGIS Usecase

NASA AMMOS Multi-Mission Geographic Information System (MMGIS)

Contact: fred.calef@jpl.nasa.gov

tariq.k.soliman@jpl.nasa.gov

Search: NASA AMMOS MMGIS

Source code: <https://github.com/NASA-AMMOS/MMGIS>

Documentation: <https://nasa-ammos.github.io/MMGIS/>

Extended Slide-Deck: <https://tinyurl.com/mmgis>

2024 MMGIS Team

F. Calef III (PI), T. Soliman (Lead Developer), J. Roberts, A. Chung, and P. Ramirez

Jet Propulsion Laboratory
California Institute of Technology

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MMGIS: Open Source Across Missions

- Deployments at NASA (AMES, JPL, JSC), ESA, Scripps Institution of Oceanography
- Each mission contributes code and functionality used by the next mission (and vice-versa)
- Open formats allow broader support (GeoJSON, GeoTIFF, TMS Tiles, Vector Tiles, 3D Tiles)
- Open source libraries/frameworks, and programs (Leaflet, three.js, GDAL, Python) allow direct & expedient code modification/bug fixes
- Web-based for large, distributed science and engineering teams
- Only download what you need at the resolution necessary
- Think multi-mission to reduce technical debt
- Cloud capable, but not cloud locked

MARS 2020 PERSEVERANCE

Collaborative Mapping

Collaboration Tools

3D Model Support

Time Series Charting

Support Earth Missions

2D GPR Elevation Models Visualization

Viewsheds Drawing Tools

Websockets

Time Aware Layers

Time Aware Raster Series

Multiple

Line-of-Sight Analysis

Cooperative Autonomous Distributed Robotic Explorers

Real-Time Ops Support Polar Projections

Time Aware Layers

This document has been reviewed and determined not to contain export controlled technical data.

National Aeronautics and
Space Administration

SHERPA

System Health Enabled
Realtime Planning Advisor

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Evan Astle, Wyatt Cannon

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NASA Ames Research Center

What is SHERPA?

- ▶ SHERPA (System Health Enabled Real-time Planning Advisor) is an artificial intelligence (AI) decision support system for space missions that is based on formal decision making under uncertainty.
- ▶ Supports planning for vehicles/systems with degrading or faulty components.
- ▶ Is model-based and adaptable to different types of missions and use cases.
- ▶ Currently serving as the primary strategic mission planning system on the VIPER lunar mission.

- ▶ On VIPER, SHERPA has been used extensively in selecting the mission area, the landing site, and in system engineering studies.
- ▶ Is currently being used to generate both nominal and contingency strategic mission plans.
- ▶ During the mission, will be used to monitor plan execution and make strategic mission plan adjustments.
- ▶ Current capabilities provide a shovel-ready basis for:
 1. Increased interactivity and results explanation
 2. Multi-agent missions
 3. Pre-computed policies for systems with limited computing resources
 4. High-granularity activity management

SHERPA is the first AI system based on formal decision making under uncertainty to be used on a space mission.

<https://blogs.nasa.gov/artemis/2023/12/01/part-1-artificial-intelligence-and-nasas-first-robotic-lunar-rover/>

<https://blogs.nasa.gov/artemis/2023/12/14/part-2-artificial-intelligence-and-nasas-first-robotic-lunar-rover/>